

A commentary on the 2x2 matrix KdV equation

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Abstract

This work demonstrates that the cnoidal wave solution of the 2x2 matrix KdV equation turns out to be a logarithmic derivative of a 2x2-matrix, whereby the matrix elements are Neville theta functions.

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Let U and V denote linear operators, and $U+V$ and UV are the sum and product, respectively. We call

$$U_t + 3U_x U_x + U_{xxx} = A \quad (1)$$

the operator valued KdV equation with unknown operator U and given constant operator A . The classical work on operator valued soliton-like equations is Marčenko [4]. For further reading please see [1] and [6].

Let $\theta_p(z|\tau)$, $p = s, c, d, n$ denote the four Neville theta functions, see [3, 20.1]. Here we assume that the argument z is real and $\Im \tau > 0$ applies to the lattice parameter τ . Derivatives regarding z are abbreviated with θ_p' . We will require the properties

$$\theta_s^2 + \theta_c^2 = \theta_n^2, \quad (2)$$

see [3, 20.4.6, 20.7.3] and

$$\theta_s' \theta_c - \theta_s \theta_c' = \theta_d \theta_n, \quad (3)$$

see [3, 20.11] and [2, 3.1.]. We state

$$\Theta(z|\tau) = \begin{bmatrix} \theta_c(z|\tau) & -\theta_s(z|\tau) \\ \theta_s(z|\tau) & \theta_c(z|\tau) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (4)$$

Then

$$\Theta^{-1}\Theta' = \begin{bmatrix} \theta_n'/\theta_n & -\theta_d/\theta_n \\ \theta_d/\theta_n & \theta_n'/\theta_n \end{bmatrix}, \quad (5)$$

because

$$\Theta^{-1}\Theta' = \frac{1}{\theta_n^2} \begin{bmatrix} \theta_c & -\theta_s \\ \theta_s & \theta_c \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \theta_c' & -\theta_s' \\ \theta_s' & \theta_c' \end{bmatrix} = \frac{1}{\theta_n^2} \begin{bmatrix} \theta_c \theta_c' + \theta_s \theta_s' & -\theta_s' \theta_c + \theta_s \theta_c' \\ \theta_s' \theta_c - \theta_s \theta_c' & \theta_c \theta_c' + \theta_s \theta_s' \end{bmatrix}.$$

To simplify the further considerations, we introduce the Jacobian elliptic function

$$\operatorname{dn}(z, k) = \frac{\theta_d(z, |\tau)}{\theta_n(z|\tau)}, \quad \tau = i \frac{K(k')}{K(k)}, \quad (6)$$

see [3, 22.2.11, 12]. Here $K(k)$ and $E(k)$ denote the complete elliptic integrals of the first and second orders, respectively, and k and k' are complementaries moduli to each other. Let $k' = \sqrt{1 - k^2}$. Then it holds that

$$\frac{d}{dz} \ln \theta_n(z|\tau) = \int_0^z \operatorname{dn}^2(\zeta, k) d\zeta - \frac{E(k)}{K(k)} z, \quad (7)$$

see [3, 22.16.17,30]. Hence

$$\Theta^{-1}\Theta' = \begin{bmatrix} \int_0^z \operatorname{dn}^2(\zeta, k) d\zeta & -\operatorname{dn}(z, k) \\ \operatorname{dn}(z, k) & \int_0^z \operatorname{dn}^2(\zeta, k) d\zeta \end{bmatrix} - \frac{E(k)}{K(k)} z \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (8)$$

Note that, we have actually eliminated the θ symbols from the logarithmic derivative of Θ . Thus we can use the well-known differential equations

$$(\operatorname{dn}')^2 = (1 - \operatorname{dn}^2)(\operatorname{dn}^2 - k'^2) \quad (9)$$

and

$$\operatorname{dn}'' = (1 + k'^2) \operatorname{dn} - 2\operatorname{dn}^3. \quad (10)$$

see [3, 22.13.3, 15]. From here it follows

$$(\operatorname{dn}^2)'' = -6\operatorname{dn}^4 + 4(1 + k'^2) \operatorname{dn}^2 - 2k'^2. \quad (11)$$

From now on, we set

$$c = 6 \left(1 + \frac{E(k)}{K(k)} \right) - (1 + k'^2) \quad (12)$$

and

$$A = \left\{ k'^2 + 3 \left(1 + \frac{E(k)}{K(k)} \right)^2 \right\} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (13)$$

The result then follows from the lemma.

Lemma 1. *The logarithmic derivative $U(z|\tau) = \Theta^{-1} \frac{d}{dz} \Theta(z|\tau)$ of*

$$\Theta(z|\tau) = \begin{bmatrix} \theta_c(z|\tau) & -\theta_s(z|\tau) \\ \theta_s(z|\tau) & \theta_c(z|\tau) \end{bmatrix}$$

is a solution of

$$cU' + 3U'U' + U''' = A. \quad (14)$$

Proof. From (8), (9) we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} U'^2 &= \begin{bmatrix} \operatorname{dn}^2 - \left(1 + \frac{E(k)}{K(k)}\right) & -\operatorname{dn}' \\ \operatorname{dn}' & \operatorname{dn}^2 - \left(1 + \frac{E(k)}{K(k)}\right) \end{bmatrix}^2 \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} 2\operatorname{dn}^4 - \left\{2\left(1 + \frac{E(k)}{K(k)}\right) + (1 + k'^2)\right\} \operatorname{dn}^2 + \left\{\left(1 + \frac{E(k)}{K(k)}\right)^2 + k'^2\right\} & -\dots \\ 2\left(\operatorname{dn}^2 - \left(1 + \frac{E(k)}{K(k)}\right)\right) \operatorname{dn}' & \dots \end{bmatrix}, \end{aligned}$$

and from (10), (11) we have

$$U''' = \begin{bmatrix} (\operatorname{dn}^2)'' & -\operatorname{dn}''' \\ \operatorname{dn}''' & (\operatorname{dn}^2)'' \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -6\operatorname{dn}^4 + 4(1 + k'^2) \operatorname{dn}^2 - 2k'^2 & -\dots \\ (1 + k'^2) \operatorname{dn}' - 6\operatorname{dn}^2 \operatorname{dn}' & \dots \end{bmatrix}.$$

□

Proposition 2. *Let $a \in \mathbb{R}$. The logarithmic derivative $U(x, t|\tau) = \Theta^{-1} \Theta_x(ax + a^3 ct|\tau)$ is a solution of*

$$U_t + 3U_x U_x + U_{xxx} = a^4 A.$$

Remark 3. In borderline cases $k \rightarrow 1$ it holds $K(k) \rightarrow \infty$, $K(k') \rightarrow \frac{\pi}{2}$, and $\operatorname{dn}(z, k) \rightarrow \operatorname{sech}(z)$, see for instance [3, 22.5.ii, 4]. The identities (3)-(12) are maintained, if θ_p , $p = s, c, d, n$ replaced by $\sinh, 1, 1, \operatorname{sech}$, respectively. Thus, the assumptions of the proposition are satisfied, i.e. the logarithmic derivative $U(x, t) = \Theta^{-1} \Theta_x(ax + a^3 ct)$ of

$$\Theta(z) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -\sinh(z) \\ \sinh(z) & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

is a solution of (1) with $c = 5$ and $A = 3a^3 \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$. As expected we obtain the well-known 1-soliton solution

$$U(x, t) = \begin{bmatrix} \tanh(ax + a^3 ct) & -\operatorname{sech}(ax + a^3 ct) \\ \operatorname{sech}(ax + a^3 ct) & \tanh(ax + a^3 ct) \end{bmatrix}$$

of (1).

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